

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lung metastasis: DUSP10.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the lung in breast cancer is difficult to treat and heterogeneous in nature, complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer, DUSP10, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of lung metastasis.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: DUSP10.

Results

Figure 1: DUSP10 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
11221	2.00E-01	0.715	-1.28081	-0.9161209	524.93	DUSP10	7954/22997	65.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of dual specificity phosphatase 10, encoded by *DUSP10* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of DUSP10 changed more than 65% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of DUSP10 messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of DUSP10 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of DUSP10 likely defined the lung metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of DUSP10, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasize size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

References

1. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Siegel, P.M., Bos, P.D., Shu, W., Giri, D.D., Viale, A., Olshen, A.B., Gerald, W.L. and Massagué, J., 2005. Genes that mediate breast cancer metastasis to lung. *Nature*, 436(7050), pp.518-524.
2. Zardavas, D., Irrthum, A., Swanton, C. and Piccart, M., 2015. Clinical management of breast cancer heterogeneity. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 12(7), pp.381-394.
3. Poste, G., Tzeng, J., Doll, J., Greig, R., Rieman, D. and Zeidman, I., 1982. Evolution of tumor cell heterogeneity during progressive growth of individual lung metastases. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 79(21), pp.6574-6578.
4. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Padua, D., Bos, P., Nguyen, D.X., Nuyten, D., Kreike, B., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Ishwaran, H. and Foekens, J.A., 2007. Lung metastasis genes couple breast tumor size and metastatic spread. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(16), pp.6740-6745.
5. Brown, D.M. and Ruoslahti, E., 2004. Metadherin, a cell surface protein in breast tumors that mediates lung metastasis. *Cancer cell*, 5(4), pp.365-374.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. GSE191230: Ong, L.T., Lee, W.C., Ma, S., Oguz, G., Niu, Z., Bao, Y., Yusuf, M., Lee, P.L., Goh, J.Y., Wang, P. and Yong, K.S.M., 2022. IFI16-dependent STING signaling is a crucial regulator of anti-HER2 immune response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(31), p.e2201376119.
10. GSE56493: Tobin, N.P., Lundberg, A., Lindström, L.S., Harrell, J.C., Foukakis, T., Carlsson, L., Einbeigi, Z., Linderholm, B.K., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Fernö, M., 2017. PAM50 provides prognostic information when applied to the lymph node metastases of advanced breast cancer patients. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 23(23), pp.7225-7231,:
11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE191230 (9) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods. When data for GSE56493 is not present, it failed to satisfy validation, and was consulted but omitted.